

STUDIES ON COLOUR AND CONSTITUTION. PART I. VERIFICATION OF FORSTER'S AND KNOTT'S RULES

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Verification of Forster's and Knott's rules has been achieved with the help of the absorption maximum data of the following groups of compounds: (a) unsymmetrical cyanines and their aza analogues, (b) *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dyes and their aza analogues, (c) merocarbocyanines and their aza analogues, and (d) *p*-dialkylaminobenzylidene derivatives of ketomethylene compounds and their aza analogues.

The present investigation deals with verification of Forster's rule (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1939, 45, 548) and Knott's rule (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1024) which correlate structural change at any point lying between two auxochromic atoms with light absorption of the concerned dye. Several unsatisfactory rules were also put forward by Lewis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 770; Lewis and Calvin, *Chem. Rev.*, 1939, 25, 273). Knott's rule may be more correctly regarded as a corollary to Forster's rule.

Forster's rule is applicable to ionic dyes and it states that the absorption maximum of the dye will increase with the decreasing tendency of the chain of chromophoric atoms lying between two auxochromes to take up the characteristic charge. The relative contributions of the participating structures in a resonance hybrid determine the nature of the charge and its distribution on the chromophoric atoms. But since the chromophoric atoms carry charges only in the excited state, it follows that the absorption maximum will increase with increase in energy of the interauxochromic, ionic excited structure.

Before applying the rule to specific examples, it is necessary to consider all the possible structures contributing to the hybrid and to assess the effect of a particular structural change on the significance of each structure. A structural change in all cases appears to increase the contribution of some structures and to decrease that of others. The change in absorption maximum following such a structural change will therefore be the resultant of the effects of the contributions of all the participating structures causing both hypsochromic and bathochromic shifts.

Knott's rule, on the other hand, is rather empirical and has its basis in Forster's rule. It states that if the carbon atom, at which replacement takes place, is separated from the active auxochromic atoms by an odd number of conjugated atoms, a hypsochromic shift results, whilst a separation by an even number of atoms results in a bathochromic shift.

The following groups of compounds were prepared to verify the theoretical observations of Forster and Knott:

- (a) Merocarbocyanines derived from pyrazolone, isoxazolone, and rhodanines as the acidic nuclei and 4-phenylthiazole as the basic nucleus and their aza analogues.
- (b) *p*-Dimethylaminobenzylidene derivatives of ketomethylene compounds and their aza analogues.
- (c) *p*-Dialkylaminostyryl dyes and their aza analogues.
- (d) Unsymmetrical cyanines and their aza analogues.

The merocarbocyanines (I: X=CH) were prepared by condensing either (i) the 5-ethoxymethylene-ketomethylene compounds (formed by the reaction of the ketomethylene compounds with triethyl orthoformate in acetic anhydride) with 4-phenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide or (ii) 2-(2-acetanilidovinyl)-4-phenylthiazole methiodide (formed by the reaction of 4-phenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide with diphenylformamidine in acetic anhydride) with the ketomethylene compound in absolute ethanol and triethylamine. The corresponding aza analogues (I: X=N) were prepared by the reaction of 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole methiodide and the 5-ethoxymethylene-ketomethylene compound in absolute ethanol and triethylamine.

In the dyes of the type (I), excited structures carrying C^- have greater significance than structures carrying C^+ , because structures carrying C^- contain one double bond more than the structures carrying C^+ . When $=CH-$ is replaced by $=N-$, the relative contribution of (Ib: X=N) to the resonance hybrid will be more than (Ib: X=CH) because of the greater stability of $-N^-$ as compared to $-CH^-$. According to Forster's rule, the increasing tendency of the methin chain to retain the characteristic charge would result in decrease in absorption maximum. Hence replacement of $=CH-$ by $=N-$ in (I) would result in a hypsochromic shift. This has actually been realised by measuring the absorption maxima data (Table I).

TABLE I

*Nature of nucleus B.	λ_{max}		Expected shift.	Observed shift.
	X=CH	X=N.		
Rhodanine		470 $m\mu$	Hypsochromic	
3-Phenylrhodanine	510 $m\mu$	485	Do	-25 $m\mu$
3- <i>o</i> -Tolylrhodanine		485		
3- <i>p</i> -Tolylrhodanine		480		
3- <i>m</i> -Tolylrhodanine		480		
3-Ethylrhodanine		480		
3- <i>m</i> -Chlorophenylrhodanine		478		
1-Phenyl-5-methylpyrazolone	501	490	Do	-11
3-Phenylisooxazolone	496	490	Do	-6

* Vide structure (Ib).

Forster's rule has also been verified by preparing the compounds of category (b). The *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene derivatives of ketomethylene compound (II: X=CH) were prepared by condensing the ketomethylene compounds with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in absolute ethanol in presence of piperidine. The corresponding aza analogues were prepared by reaction of the heterocyclic ketomethylene compounds with *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline. The various carbonyl-containing nuclei included in the present investigation are isooxazolone, pyrazolone, rhodanine, and thiohydantoin.

In these compounds, the significant excited structure involves $-X^{\pm}$ and not $-X^{-}$ as in (I). For the replacement of $=CH-$ by $=N-$, the relative contribution of (IIb: X=N) to the resonance hybrid will be less than (IIb: X=CH) because of the greater stability of $-CH^{\pm}$ as compared to $-N^{\pm}$. Therefore in accordance with Forster's rule, a bathochromic shift is predicted for such structural change from $=CH-$ to $=N-$. The experimental data recorded in Table II are in agreement with the theoretical observations made above.

TABLE II

Nature of nucleus A*.	$\lambda_{\text{max.}}$		**Observed shift.
	X=CH.	X=N.	
3-Phenylisooxazolone	490 $m\mu$	545 $m\mu$	55 $m\mu$
1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone	470	520	50
3-Phenylrhodanine	480	505	25
3- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-2-thiohydantoin	450	470	20

* Vide structure (IIa).

** Bathochromic shift in all cases as expected.

The same conclusions are also reached from a study of the absorption maximum data *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dyes. The *p*-dimethylaminostyryl dyes (III: X=CH) were prepared by condensing the methiodides of the heterocyclic bases with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in abso-

lute ethanol and piperidine. The aza analogues (III: X=N) were prepared by the action of the quaternary salts on *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline.

In (III), the most likely excited structure involves $-X^{\pm}$ and not $-X^{-}$, on the basis of considerations which hold good in case of (II) and also β -anilino-vinyl derivatives and its aza analogues (Knott, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1586). And as $-CH^{\pm}$ is more stable than $-N^{\pm}$, such replacement of $=CH-$ by $=N-$, in accordance with Forster's rule, should result in a bathochromic shift as observed in (II). The experimental results recorded in Table III justify the theoretical observations made above. It is interesting to note that in these compounds (III), the chromophoric atom at which the replacement takes place is separated from the active auxochromic atoms by an even number of conjugated atoms, and Knott's rule predicts a bathochromic shift for such compounds.

TABLE III

Nature of nucleus A.

Nature of nucleus A.	λ_{max}		*Observed shift.
	X=CH.	X=N.	
Quinoline-2	527 $m\mu$	590 $m\mu$	63 $m\mu$
4-Phenylthiazole	490	530	40
4- <i>p</i> -Bromophenylthiazole	490	540	50
4- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenylthiazole	490	530	40
Pyridine-2	459	490	31

* Bathochromic shift in all cases as expected.

Consideration of the absorption data of unsymmetrical cyanines and their aza analogues as demonstrated the soundness and general applicability of both the rules. In these compounds (IV),

the chromophoric atom at which replacement takes place is separated from the active auxochromic atoms by an odd number of conjugated atoms. Hence Knott's rule predicts a hypsochromic shift.

In the structure (IV), the negative charge in $-\text{N}^-$ (IVb: $\text{X}=\text{N}$) is retained with more ease than in $-\text{CH}^-$ (IVb: $\text{X}=\text{CH}$). Hence the azacyanine, in accordance with Forster's rule, would absorb at a lower wave length than the corresponding unsymmetrical cyanine. The experimental results in Table IV confirm the above theoretical observations.

TABLE IV

Nature of nucleus A.	Nature of nucleus B.	Value of n.	$\lambda_{\text{max.}}$		* Observed shift.
			X=CH.	X=N.	
Benzothiazole ^a	4-Phenyl-T †	0	418 $m\mu$	375 $m\mu$	-43 $m\mu$
Quinoline-2-e	"	0	475	405	-70
Benzothiazole	"	1	540	470	-70
Quinoline-2	"	1	600	520	-80
Benzothiazole	"	2	640	565	-75
"	Benzo-T	2	660	580	-80
"	4-p-Bromophenyl-T	2	640	590	-50
"	4-p-Ethoxyphenyl-T	2	640	560	-80
Quinoline-2	4-Phenyl-T	2	700	590	-110
"	4-p-Bromophenyl-T	2	695	590	-105
Benzothiazole	4-Phenyl-T	3	740	655	-85
"	4-p-Ethoxyphenyl-T	3	740	650	-90
Quinoline-2	4-Phenyl-T	3	790	670	-120
"	4-p-Bromophenyl-T	3	790	670	^e 120

† T denotes thiazole.

* Hypsochromic shift in all cases as expected.

EXPERIMENTAL

5-(3'-Methyl-4'-phenylthiazolin-2'-ylidene-aminomethylene)-3-p-tolylrhodanine.—4-Phenyl-2-aminothiazole methiodide (1.6 g.) and 5-ethoxymethylene-3-p-tolylrhodanine (1.4 g.) were boiled in absolute ethanol and triethylamine for 30 minutes. After removing excess of the solvent, the product was washed with and recrystallised from absolute ethanol, m.p. 230-31°, yield 45%. (Found: C, 59.53; H, 3.87. $C_{21}H_{17}ON_2S_2$ requires C, 59.58; H, 4.02%).

The analytical data of the compounds derived from other ketomethylene nuclei are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

Aza analogues of merocarboyanines.

Nature of R†.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
H	50%	*233°	$C_{14}H_{11}ON_2S_2$	50.33	50.40	3.21	3.30
Phenyl	40	300°	$C_{20}H_{15}ON_2S_2$	58.37	58.53	3.72	3.90
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	40	*224-26°	$C_{21}H_{17}ON_2S_2$	59.40	59.58	4.10	4.08
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	45	221-22°	$C_{21}H_{17}ON_2S_2$	59.50	59.58	3.83	4.02
Ethyl	60	192-93°	$C_{16}H_{13}ON_2S_2$	53.31	53.49	4.03	4.17
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	40	300°	$C_{20}H_{13}ON_2S_2Cl$	53.81	54.00	3.18	3.37

† Vide structure (I a : X=N).

* Melted with decomposition.

5-(*p*-Dimethylaminoanilinomethylene)-3-*m*-tolyl-2-thiohydantoin.—3-*m*-Tolylthiohydantoin (0.4 g.) and *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline (0.3 g.) were boiled in absolute ethanol in presence of piperidine for 1 hour. The desired product, separated on cooling, was recrystallised from ethanol in orange-brown needles, m.p. 249°, yield 50%. (Found: C, 63.80; H, 5.11. $C_{19}H_{19}ON_2S$ requires C, 63.91; H, 5.33%).

The analytical data of other compounds are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI

Aza analogues of p-dimethylaminobenzylidene derivatives of ketomethylene compounds.

Nature of nucleus A*.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
3-Phenylrhodanine	70%	145°	$C_{17}H_{13}ON_2S_2$	59.81	59.72	4.41	4.33
3-Phenylisoxazolone	70	136°	$C_{17}H_{13}O_2N_2$	69.61	69.50	5.12	5.34
1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone	60	147°	$C_{18}H_{14}ON_4$	70.60	70.43	5.88	5.64

* Vide structure (II: X=N).

2-(*p*-Dimethylaminoanilinomethylene)-3-methyl-4-phenylthiazole Iodide.—4-Phenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (0.64 g.) and *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline (0.3 g.) were boiled in absolute ethanol in presence of piperidine (2 drops) for 30 minutes. The desired product separating on removal

of excess of solvent was recrystallised from ethanol in pink needles, m.p. 209°, yield 50%. (Found : C, 50.64 ; H, 4.23. $C_{19}H_{20}N_3IS$ requires C, 50.78 ; H, 4.45%.)

The analytical data of other such compounds are shown in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Aza analogues of p-dimethylaminostyryl dyes.

Nature of nucleus A.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
4- <i>p</i> -Bromophenylthiazole	45%	193°	$C_{19}H_{19}N_3BrIS$	43.18	43.00	3.56	3.40
4- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenylthiazole	55	190°	$C_{19}H_{19}N_3ClIS$	47.17	47.03	3.81	3.48
Quinoline-2	50	195°	$C_{18}H_{18}N_3I$	54.68	54.53	4.80	4.62
Pyridine-2	50	178°	$C_{18}H_{18}N_3I$	49.05	48.83	4.90	5.05

[3-Methyl-2-benzothiazole] [3-methyl-2-(4-phenylthiazole)]-8-azamethincyanine Iodide.—2-Mercaptobenzothiazole methiodide (0.32 g.) and 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole methiodide (0.32 g.) were boiled in absolute ethanol and triethylamine for 10 minutes. The product separating on cooling was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 246°, yield 45%. (Found : C, 46.32 ; H, 3.29. $C_{18}H_{18}N_3IS_2$ requires C, 46.45 ; H, 3.44%.)

[3-Methyl-2-benzothiazole] [3-methyl-2-(4-phenylthiazole)]-10-azatrimethincyanine Iodide.—4-Phenyl-2-aminothiazole methiodide (0.32 g.) and 2-(2-acetanilidovinyl)-benzothiazole methiodide (Patnaik and Rout, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 511) (0.44 g.) were boiled in dry pyridine for 5 minutes. The desired product separated on addition of water. It was recrystallised twice from ethanol in brown needles, m.p. 210-11°, yield 50%. (Found : C, 48.64 ; H, 3.50. $C_{20}H_{18}N_3IS_2$ requires C, 48.87 ; H, 3.66%.)

[3-Methyl-2-benzothiazole] [3-methyl-2-(4-phenylthiazole)]-12-azapentamethincyanine Iodide.—2-(4-Acetanilido-1 : 3-butadienyl)-benzothiazole methiodide (Patnaik and Rout, *loc. cit.*) (0.46 g.) and 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole methiodide (0.32 g.) were boiled in dry pyridine in presence of triethylamine for 7 minutes. The desired product separated on pouring to water. It was recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 160°, yield 50%. (Found : C, 50.90 ; H, 3.64. $C_{22}H_{20}N_3IS_2$ requires C, 51.06 ; H, 3.87%.)

[3-Methyl-2-benzothiazole] [3-methyl-2-(4-phenylthiazole)]-14-azaseptamethincyanine Iodide.—4-Phenyl-2-aminothiazole methiodide (0.32 g.) and 2-(6-acetanilido-1 : 3 : 5-hexatrienyl)-benzothiazole methiodide (Patnaik and Rout, *loc. cit.*) (0.49 g.) were boiled in absolute ethanol and triethylamine for 5 minutes. The desired product separated on chilling. It was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 175-76°, yield 45%. (Found : C, 52.88 ; H, 3.90. $C_{24}H_{22}N_3IS_2$ requires C, 53.04 ; H, 4.05%.)

The analytical data of other azacyanines are shown in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII
Unsymmetrical azacyanines.

*Nature of nucleus A.	*Nature of nucleus B.	Value of <i>n</i> .	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Quinoline-2	4-Phenyl-T	0	50%	246-47°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ IS	52.29	52.20	3.93	3.81
..	..	1	55	217-18°	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₃ IS	54.43	54.30	4.12	4.01
Benzothiazole	Benzo-T	2	40	250-51°	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₃ IS ₂	50.86	50.70	4.21	4.10
..	4- <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-T	2	60	135°	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ ON ₃ IS ₂	50.46	50.23	4.01	3.91
..	4- <i>p</i> -Bromophenyl-T	2	60	185-86°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ BrIS ₂	44.30	44.16	3.19	3.03
..	4- <i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl-T	2	50	175-76°	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ ON ₃ IS ₂	51.34	51.17	4.28	4.10
Quinoline-2	4-Phenyl-T	2	40	195°	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ N ₃ IS	56.37	56.19	4.30	4.20
Benzothiazole	4- <i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl-T	3	45	212-13°	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ ON ₃ IS ₂	53.16	53.02	4.43	4.22
Quinoline-2	4-Phenyl-T	3	50	210-12°	C ₂₉ H ₂₇ N ₃ IS	58.10	58.02	4.47	4.30

Vide Table IV for the structures (X=N).⁷

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